

THE ADVANTAGES AND FEATURES OF TEACHING AND LEARNING
ONLINE IN THE EDUCATION PROCESS

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Abstract. *This is an interactive, collaborative teaching approach that involves creating a learning process between students and teachers. It allows for lectures to be delivered from high to low collaboration levels and engages passive students. The focus of this approach is to engage students in a collaborative effort, where they learn to "create together." The approach activates students to take on an active learning role, instead of being passive recipients of information, which is what is usually required for standard testing.*

Keywords: *creativity, assessment, approaches, ability, competence, research, analysis.*

Online learning is the newest and most popular form of distance education today. Within the past decade it has had a major impact on postsecondary education and the trend is only increasing. In this workshop we will explore what the experience of online learning is like for students and how it has changed the role of the instructor. Online learning is education that takes place over the Internet. It is often referred to as “elearning” among other terms. However, online learning is just one type of “distance learning” - the umbrella term for any learning that takes place across distance and not in a traditional classroom. Distance learning has a long history and there are several types available today, including:

- Correspondence Courses: conducted through regular mail with little interaction.
- Telecourses: where content is delivered via radio or television broadcast.
- CD-ROM Courses: where the student interacts with static computer content.
- Online Learning: Internet-based courses offered synchronously and/or asynchronously.
- Mobile Learning: by means of devices such as cellular phones, PDAs and digital audio players (iPods, MP3 players).

In years past, instructors had to create their “virtual classrooms” from scratch which was difficult and often led to poor results. Today, an entire industry has emerged to do this for us. Course Management System (CMS) software is utilized by just about all colleges today. CMS allow instructors to design and deliver their courses within a flexible framework that includes a number of different tools to enable learning and communication to occur. Popular for-profit CMS include:

- Blackboard (www.blackboard.com)
- WebCT (www.webct.com)
- eCollege (www.college.com)

Any of these CMS offer functionality which allows instructors to deliver course content, enable communications, and conduct evaluations. The most common tools offered by CMS include:

Schedule	For posting and viewing deadlines, events, etc.
Announcements	For posting current information to all students.
Syllabus	For creating and posting the course syllabus.
Modules	For publishing and viewing course content in sections.

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Assignments	For posting, submitting, and grading student work.
Discussion Board	For asynchronous discussions, group work, and collaboration.
Private Messages	For private communication between students and/or the instructor.
Chat	For real-time, synchronous conversation in written form.

Online learning is catalyzing a pedagogical shift in how we teach and learn. There is a shift away from top-down lecturing and passive students to a more interactive, collaborative approach in which students and instructor co-create the learning process. The Instructor’s role is changing from the “sage on the stage” to “the guide on the side.” This point of view maintains that people actively construct new knowledge as they interact with their environment. This is a student-centered approach in which students “co-create” their learning experience. This approach empowers students as active learners instead of just passive recipients absorbing information and reproducing it for standardized tests. Constructionism asserts that learning is particularly effective when constructing something for others to experience. This can be anything from a spoken sentence or an internet posting, to more complex things like a painting or a presentation. For example, you might read this page several times and still forget it by tomorrow - but if you were asked to explain these ideas to someone else in your own words, or produce a slideshow that explained these concepts, you would gain a deeper understanding that is more integrated into your own ideas.

Collaboration

As an instructor, you focus on the experiences that would best generate learning from the learner's point of view, rather than just publishing and assessing the information you think they need to know. Each participant in a course can and should be a teacher as well as a learner. Your job changes from being the sole source of knowledge, to being a guide and role model. You connect with students in ways that address their own learning needs by moderating discussions and activities in a way that collectively leads students towards the larger learning goals of the class.

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